

Determination of Iodine in Marine Algae

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A new technique has been developed for the quick fixation and rapid analysis of iodine in seaweed. The method consists of digesting the seaweed with 10% potassium hydroxide in a domestic model pressure cooker for 10 min. After cooling, the material is dried and ashed at 500°. The ash is extracted with hot water and iodine determined iodometrically. The technique is applicable to all the types of the seaweeds.

MORE and more interest is now evinced to explore and tap the indigenous resources of iodine as large quantities of iodine are imported¹ every year to cater to country's (India) pharmaceutical and iodised salt requirements. Besides the main source, Chile salt petre, iodine is also extracted from brown marine algae in France, Norway, Java and Japan. Marine algae found around the Indian coast have also been analysed by different workers²⁻⁶ from time to time.

Although iodine is known to be present in seaweed for more than 150 years, its analysis is still a long and a tedious process. The first recorded analysis of iodine in seaweed is in 1834 and involves the burning of seaweed to obtain ash which is subsequently analysed iodometrically. Till recently the estimation of iodine has also been based on the same old process of preparing⁸ the kelp from the weed. Modification of the procedure of burning^{9,10} or subsequent oxidation of ash extract by common oxidising agents¹¹ like chlorine, bromine, nitric oxide, hypochlorite etc. had also been proposed.

Kappanna and Rao⁶ extended the method of analysis of iodine in food materials¹² to its analysis in seaweeds. The method consists of fixing the iodine of the seaweed by refluxing for 24 hr with alcoholic potash solution. The refluxed material is

dried and ashed at 500° to remove the carbonaceous material and iodine determined iodometrically. The present studies were, undertaken to find a quick and equally reliable method for the routine estimation of iodine in all types of seaweeds. The results obtained by the present digestion technique are compared with standard alcoholic potash method and also with direct burning of seaweed, adopted earlier.

Experimental

In the first set of experiments the known amounts of seaweeds were taken in silica crucible and ashed in the furnace at 450°-500°. The iodine was extracted by boiling with 150 ml of distilled water. The iodine in the water extract was subsequently determined iodometrically.

The loss of iodine by directly burning the seaweeds varies within wide limits (Table 1). The loss even in the different species of the same genera is also not uniform, indicating that the samples were collected at different stages of development during the life cycle of the weed.

Another set of experiments were performed by digesting the seaweed either as such or in the presence of a fixative, under pressure in a domestic modle

TABLE I—ESTIMATION OF IODINE IN SEAWEEDS BY DIRECT BURNING (AT 500°), DIGESTION TECHNIQUE AND BY STANDARD ALCOHOLIC POTASH METHOD

Name of seaweed	Place of collection	Iodine estimated mg/100 g		
		by direct burning	by digestion technique	by alcoholic potash method
<i>Sargassum</i> spp.	Sikka	35.3	42.27	42.30
<i>Sargassum</i> spp.	Kanyakumari 1971	30.1	53.36	53.35
<i>Sargassum</i> spp.	—	—	38.84	38.90
<i>Sargassum cinereum</i>	Sikka	26.1	45.32	45.35
<i>Sargassum tenerrimum</i>	Okha 1968	31.4	59.42	59.54
<i>Sargassum wightii</i>	Mandapam 1972	64.4	74.90	74.90
<i>Cystoseira indica</i>	Okha 1968	27.5	40.01	39.99
<i>Spathoglossum variable</i>	Okha 1968	—	23.10	23.05
<i>Asparagopsis</i> spp.	Okha 1971	—	525.80	526.30
<i>Gracilaria corticata</i>	Dwarka 1968	5.1	10.98	11.05
<i>Hypnea musciformis</i>	Okha 1967	—	28.87	28.83
Filter cake of alginic acid plant (from M/s. Cellulose Products, Ahmedabad)	—	5.9	17.46	17.62

pressure cooker (Hawakin) capable of developing a pressure of one kg per square centimeter. About 8-10 g of the sample of seaweed was taken in a stainless steel bowl (400 ml capacity). 50 ml of 10% potassium hydroxide solution was added and the bowl kept in the pressure cooker. The cooker was then heated and the steam pressure allowed to be built inside. The pressure was maintained for 10 min. After cooling the sample was cooled, dried and ash at 500° and the iodine determined in the ash.

Lower concentrations of fixative (KOH) did not produce quantitative results. Sodium hydroxide (10%) and saturated solution of lime water under similar conditions were also found to be less effective. Ten minutes digestion has been found to be most optimum but the longer digestion periods did not affect the results.

The above technique originally worked out for *Sargassum* was extended to other seaweeds of red and brown algae and was found equally effective. Table 1 gives the analysis of different seaweeds analysed by the pressure digestions technique and the results are compared with direct burning and alcoholic potash method.

The method is also found equally suitable for iodine analysis in¹² the filter cake obtained after the extraction of alginic acid from brown seaweed with the same efficiency.

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